

kg S/ ha). Normal cultural operations were done.

The experiment was in randomized block design with four replications. Seedlings (25 d old) were transplanted 22 May at 25- × 15-cm spacing and harvested at 134 d.

Rough grain and straw yields were recorded. Samples of rough grain and straw were analyzed for protein content by the improved Kjeldahl method (N × 6.25).

There was a significant positive correlation between grain protein content and yield ($r = 0.84^{**}$) and straw protein content and yield ($r = 0.79^{**}$) (Fig. 1, 2). □

1. Correlation between rice grain yield and protein content. Chittagong, Bangladesh.

2. Correlation between rice straw yield and protein content. Chittagong, Bangladesh.

Disease resistance

Tungro (RTV) transmission and mode of green leafhopper (GLH) feeding

G. Dahal and H. Hibino, Plant Pathology Department; and R. C. Saxena, Entomology Department, IRRI

We studied the relationship between feeding behavior of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* and transmission of RTV-associated viruses in seedlings of nine rice cultivars. Newly emerged adults from a GLH colony reared on rice

Cultivar	GLH reaction	GLH (no.) that transmitted				GLH (no.) feeders on		
		5	10	15	20	Phloem + Phloem	xylem	Xylem
ASD 7	R	RTBV + RTSV	1	0	0	0	0	1
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	1	7
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	10	0	0	0	0	11
Gam Pai 30-12-15	R	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	4	2
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	6	8
Palasithari 601	R	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	4	1
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	5	10
Utri Rajapan	S	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	2	2
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	16	0
Habiganj DW8	S	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	3	0
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	17	0
TKM6	MR to MS	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	2	2
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	3	13
ARC11554	R	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	0	2
		RTSV	10	0	0	0	0	2
		None	15	0	0	0	0	16
IR22	S	RTBV + RTSV	10	0	0	0	12	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	7	0
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	10	0	0	0	1	0
TN1	S	RTBV + RTSV	10	0	0	0	8	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	9	0
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	10	0	0	0	3	0

1. Transmission of RTBV or RTSV or both by GLH and insect mode during inoculation access feeding on 9 selected rice cultivars. IRRI, 1987.

2. Scatter diagram of acidic and basic honeydew spots excreted by individual virus transmitter and nontransmitter GLH on 9 selected rice cultivars during 22 h inoculation feeding. IRRI, 1987.

cultivar TN1 were given a 4-d acquisition feeding on plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), then a 1-d inoculation feeding on individual seedlings.

Feeding behavior during inoculation access was monitored by the color reaction of honeydew spots on bromocresol-treated filter paper disks. Blue spots (basic reaction) indicated phloem feeding and brown spots (acidic reaction) indicated xylem feeding. Inoculated seedlings were individually

indexed for the presence of viruses by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Greater xylem feeding occurred in GLH-resistant cultivars ASD7, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Palasithari 601, and ARC11554 (Fig. 1). Greater phloem + xylem feeding occurred in GLH-susceptible cultivars Utri Rajapan, Habiganj DW8, IR22, and TN1. Except for ARC11554, GLH-resistant cultivars were predominantly infected with RTBV alone. On Gam Pai 30-12-15 and Palasithari 601, GLH that transmitted

viruses fed more on phloem + xylem than on xylem; on GLH-susceptible Utri Rajapan and Habiganj DW8, all GLH fed on phloem + xylem, and most failed to transmit either virus.

The areas of basic and acidic honeydew spots excreted by individual GLH on each cultivar varied (Fig. 2), indicating heterogeneity of GLH in the colony used, although the colony has been maintained on TN1 for many years. Virus transmission did not correlate with feeding sites in the scatter diagram. □